

Molecular modeling, synthesis and characterization of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes involving some Schiff base ligands

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Manuscript received 16 September 2009, revised 12 April 2010, accepted 07 July 2010

Abstract : Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the Schiff bases derived from indole-3-carboxaldehyde (indal) and DL-2-aminobutyric acid (2aba)/DL-valine (val) were modeled, synthesized and characterized by various techniques. The molecular modeling and IR studies suggest that the ligands bind the metal ions through azomethine nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen atoms. The band gap and ionization potential values indicate that indal-val is more stable than indal-2aba. The molar conductance values show that the complexes are non electrolytic. Electronic spectral data show that Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have tetrahedral geometry, while Cu^{II} complexes exhibit square planar geometry.

Keywords : Molecular modeling, Schiff base, amino acid, conductance, IR, electronic spectra.

Introduction

Transition metal complexes with oxygen and nitrogen donor Schiff bases are of particular interest because of their ability to possess unusual configurations¹. Metal complexes of heterocyclic Schiff base ligands have shown a wide range of biological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal and anti-inflammatory^{2,3}. In recent years, molecular modeling studies play an important role in the study of ligands and their complexes^{4,5}. In continuation to our earlier work on the Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes⁶⁻⁹, the present paper deals with the computational, synthesis and characterization of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with a Schiff base derived from indole-3-carboxaldehyde (indal) and DL-2-aminobutyric acid (2aba)/DL-valine (val).

Results and discussion

Computational studies :

The numbering pattern and structure of the ligands and the complexes are given in Fig. 1. Table 1 consists of the important parameters of the ligand and the complexes. The Mulliken's atomic charge density values in Table 1 demonstrate the binding atoms of the ligands to be azomethine nitrogen and the carboxylate oxygen. The band gap values are respectively 0.6020 and 0.7382 eV for indal-2aba and indal-val. Similarly the ionization po-

tential values are respectively 8.4678 and 8.6112 eV. These values indicate that indal-val is more stable than indal-2aba.

The ligands are non-planar in nature. The bond length of azomethine group and charge density of azomethine nitrogen are less in indal-val compared to those in indal-2aba. The bond angles given in Table 1 indicate that the ligands can form tetrahedral complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}, while Cu^{II} forms square planar complexes. In general M-N bond length is longer than M-O bond length. The M-N bond for indal-2aba is longer than indal-val. In the case of M-O bond lengths, indal-val has slightly longer bond length than indal-2aba. There is only slight difference in the bond angle between the complexes and ligands. The dihedral angle values indicate that the two ligands are distorted from the planarity in the complexes. The distortion is higher in the case of indal-val compared to that in indal-2aba. Thus, it can be concluded that the effect of substitution in the ligand has higher influence on steric effect rather than electronic effect.

Solid state studies :

The analytical data for the Schiff base ligands and their complexes are listed in Table 2. The results of the elemental analysis show that the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 2 and the composition is [ML₂] for all the complexes. All

Numbering pattern of the ligands

Optimized geometry of indal-2aba

Optimized geometry of indal-val

Proposed structure of the metal complexes
(M = Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II})

the complexes are stable towards air and moisture and most of the complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents and soluble in acetonitrile, DMF and DMSO.

Conductivity measurements :

The low molar conductance values of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes (Table 2) indicate that both indal-2aba and indal-val complexes are non electrolytes¹⁰.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectrum of indal-2aba and indal-val respectively shows the strong band at 1622 and 1626 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to azomethine stretching frequency. During complexation, these bands are shifted to lower frequency indicating the azomethine nitrogen coordinating the metal ion. The strong bands in the region 1597 and 1603 cm^{-1} respectively for indal-2aba and indal-val can be assigned to the asymmetric stretching frequency of carboxylato group. The bands at 1415 and 1401 cm^{-1} are due to symmetric stretching vibration of carboxylato group. On complexation with metal ions, the asymmetric and symmetric stretching bands are shifted to lower frequency for all the complexes, which reveals the formation of linkage between the metal ion and carboxylato oxygen atom. Moreover, the difference of $\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes indicates monodentate binding of the carboxylato group in all the complexes¹¹.

The spectra of the metal complexes show some new bands in the 510–550 cm^{-1} and 430–480 cm^{-1} regions, which may probably be due to the formation of M–O and M–N bonds, respectively. Thus the IR spectrum indicates that the Schiff base ligands indal-2aba and indal-val are coordinated to the metal ion in a bidentate mode and the binding sites are azomethine nitrogen and carboxylato oxygen atoms.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral data of the Schiff base ligands and their complexes in DMSO are given in Table 2. The spectra of free ligands indal-2aba and indal-val exhibit a broad band at 300, 320 nm, respectively, which can be assigned to $\Pi\text{-}\Pi^*$ transition of the azomethine ($>\text{C}=\text{N}$) chromophore. For all the complexes these bands are shifted to lower wave length, suggesting the coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom. The spectra of Co^{II} complexes with indal-2aba and indal-val respectively show bands at

Fig. 1. Numbering pattern and optimized geometry of the ligands and the structure of metal complexes.

Table 1. Important parameters of the ligands indal-2aba and indal-val and their metal complexes

	Bond length (Å)				Angle (°)		
	M-N ₁	M-N ₂	M-O ₁	M-O ₂	N ₁ -M-O ₁	N ₂ -M-O ₂	C ₁ -N ₁ -M-N ₂
Co-indal-2aba	1.8311	1.8314	1.7690	1.7689	105.421	105.403	59.3231
Ni-indal-2aba	1.8219	1.8221	1.7593	1.7593	105.661	85.66	59.520
Cu-indal-2aba	1.8363	1.8346	1.7787	1.7796	85.1638	104.7077	68.7993
Zn-indal-2aba	1.9116	1.9198	1.8550	1.8545	104.1487	106.2566	37.1663
Co-indal-val	1.8297	1.8304	1.7697	1.7689	104.885	104.846	121.654
Ni-indal-val	1.1821	1.8202	1.7596	1.7593	105.1353	105.1052	77.1284
Cu-indal-val	1.8367	1.8377	1.7790	1.7788	84.4951	84.484	78.4532
Zn-indal-val	1.9168	1.9165	1.8560	1.8558	102.762	102.7737	74.7166
	Charge density			Dipole			
	C ₁₀ =N ₁₁ (Å)	N ₁₁	O ₁₅	moment (D)			
indal-2aba	1.2908	-0.2022	-0.3275	4.525			
indal-val	1.2851	-0.1999	-0.2876	2.422			

Table 2. Analytical and physical data of the Schiff base ligands and their complexes

Ligand/ Complexes	Empirical formula and colour	Found (Calcd.) (%)					Molar conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻² mol ⁻¹)	λ _{max} (nm)
		C	H	N	O	M		
[indal-2aba]	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ K Yellow solid	59.33 (59.55)	5.32 (5.35)	9.87 (9.92)	11.05 (11.33)	-	-	283
[Co(indal-2aba) ₂]	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄ Co Violet solid	61.53 (61.65)	5.61 (5.54)	10.11 (10.27)	11.56 (11.73)	10.33 (10.80)	13	567
[Ni(indal-2aba) ₂]	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄ Ni Palegreen solid	61.60 (61.68)	5.38 (5.55)	10.15 (10.28)	11.68 (11.74)	10.67 (10.76)	17	595
[Cu(indal-2aba) ₂]	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄ Cu Bluish green	61.02 (61.13)	5.42 (5.50)	10.02 (10.18)	11.68 (11.63)	11.45 (11.55)	18	687
[Zn(indal-2aba) ₂]	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄ Zn Colourless solid	60.75 (60.93)	5.42 (5.48)	10.02 (10.15)	11.43 (11.59)	11.78 (11.85)	21	278
[indal-val]	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ K Yellow solid	58.08 (58.19)	4.73 (4.88)	10.32 (10.44)	11.87 (11.92)	-	-	303
[Co(indal-val) ₂]	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ Co Violet solid	60.24 (60.35)	4.89 (5.06)	10.75 (10.83)	12.12 (12.37)	11.21 (11.39)	12	691
[Ni(indal-val) ₂]	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ Ni Palegreen solid	60.22 (60.38)	5.23 (5.07)	10.54 (10.83)	12.32 (12.37)	11.24 (11.35)	17	564
[Cu(indal-val) ₂]	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ Cu Bluishgreen solid	59.57 (59.82)	4.88 (5.02)	10.58 (10.73)	12.12 (12.26)	12.07 (12.17)	18	717
[Zn(indal-val) ₂]	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ Zn Colourless solid	60.22 (60.38)	4.91 (5.07)	10.56 (10.83)	12.13 (12.22)	11.12 (11.35)	17	296

567 and 691 nm can be attributed to ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition for the Co^{II} tetrahedral geometry¹². The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes with indal-2aba and indal-val show only one transition respectively at 595 and 564 nm due to ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ transition for tetrahedral Ni^{II}

complexes¹². The Cu^{II} complexes in their spectra display a broad band in the 650–750 nm region which can be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition, indicating the complexes to have square planar geometry¹². Zn^{II} complexes do not exhibit *d-d* electronic transition due to the com-

pletely filled *d* orbital. Four coordinate Zn^{II} complexes, in general, would have tetrahedral geometry.

Experimental

The parameters of the ligands and the complexes were optimised respectively by semiempirical and molecular mechanics calculations. The semiempirical calculations were done by MOPAC 6 programme using AM1 Hamiltonian¹³. The molecular mechanics calculations were carried out by Hyperchem 7 package using MM⁺ method¹⁴. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Amino acids were obtained from Fluka, indole-3-carboxaldehyde was obtained from Himedia and metal(II) salts were purchased from Merck. Solvents were purified and dried before use according to the standard method¹⁵. The ligands and complexes were synthesized by the methods reported elsewhere^{7,8}. Elemental analyses were performed with Perkin-Elmer elemental analyzer. The metal contents were determined by complexometric titrations with EDTA. Conductivity measurements were made on 10⁻³ M solutions at room temperature with a coronation digital conductivity meter. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on a JASCO FT/IR-410 spectrometer in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda-25 UV-Vis spectrometer.

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